

Original Research

The Role of the Sharia Supervisory Board in Moderating the Relationship Between Sustainability Reports and Earnings Management in Islamic Banking

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Abstract

Earnings Management is manipulation to reported profit so that reported profit makes a loss No represent real economic condition of a company. This research aims to analyze certain variables for earnings management in Islamic banking. The variables tested in this study include the Sustainability Report (X1), the Sharia Supervisory Board (Z) as variables moderation to profit management (earnings management) (Y). By using purposive sampling method, sample study consists of 129. Data analysis uses Ereviews. Research results show that Sustainability reports have a negative effect on earnings management. Based on the results of the regression analysis, a probability value of $0.000 < 0.05$ was obtained, with a regression coefficient of -3.724231 . The Sharia Supervisory Board confirmed the negative influence of sustainability reports on earnings management. Based on the results of the regression analysis, the probability value was $0.7972 > 0.05$, with a regression coefficient of 12.03276 . This finding provides insight that reporting good sustainability Not only increases the company's image in the eyes of the public but can also strengthen the integrity of financial reports by pressing trend management to manipulate profits.

Keywords: Earnings Management, Sharia Supervisory Board, Sustainability Report.

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Introduction

In the modern era, where technological developments continue to advance, competition in the business world has become increasingly intense. This condition drives companies, especially management, to employ various strategies to deliver the best outcomes for both the company and its investors (Tiur, 2022). Companies must continuously innovate to remain competitive and sustain their existence. When a company shows good performance, it positively affects its value in the eyes of investors, encouraging them to invest, and vice versa.

Financial statements are a key tool used by investors to assess a company's growth, helping them decide whether to invest their capital. Among the information in financial statements, the company's profit is one of the most crucial, as it indicates the company's ability to generate earnings, including in Islamic banking institutions. Islamic banking reports are regulated under PSAK No. 101 (Indonesian Statement of Financial Accounting Standards) regarding financial accounting reports for Islamic banking. Therefore, financial reporting in Islamic banking must adhere to the established accounting standards.

In the presentation of financial statements, company management sometimes selects certain accounting methods for specific purposes, a practice often referred to as earnings management. Management actions in managing company profits have led to several corporate financial reporting scandals. These financial reporting scandals have raised serious concerns among users of financial statements. Many factors affect the occurrence of earnings management within a company, including the current financial condition and performance of the company's management.

Earnings management is not only practiced by companies but can also occur in the banking sector. Earnings management may take place in both Islamic and conventional banks, even though these two types of banks operate under different principles. In Indonesia, the banking system adopts a *dual banking system*, consisting of two types of operations: conventional banking and Islamic banking. The disclosure of financial statements in Islamic banking must be carried out transparently, as accurate and sufficient information is essential for decision-making by parties with interests in Islamic banking. One form of a bank's accountability is demonstrated through its financial statements and annual reports. Where is the reporting process located? The reporting process must be free from manipulation or managerial engineering to ensure that no parties feel disadvantaged. According to Padmantyo et al. (2010) In general, Islamic banking theory uses a profit-sharing system in its operations; however, in practice, only Islamic banks can engage in earnings management practices. Examples of earnings management practices that may occur in Islamic banks include adjusting the profit and loss sharing on deposit returns by offering incentives in the form of returns that are equivalent to the market value received by Investment Account Holders (IAH) (Padmantyo et al., 2010).

In Indonesia, earnings management practices have been found in several banks, both conventional and Islamic. Examples include the Lippo Bank case in 2002, BBCI Bank Finance, Citibank in 2011, and, more recently, in the oldest Islamic bank in Indonesia, Bank Muamalat. In 2019, Bank Muamalat was identified by the Financial Services

Authority (OJK) as engaging in earnings management in its financial reports to attract investors who could help the bank avoid bankruptcy. Bank Muamalat experienced a 95.1% year-on-year profit decline to IDR 5.1 billion and a 24.7% decrease in fund distribution income, from IDR 1.78 trillion to IDR 1.34 trillion. In 2018, Bank Muamalat's profit had increased significantly compared to the previous year. This occurred because Bank Muamalat engaged in financial engineering by selling non-performing assets through valuable securities. Thus, Bank Muamalat was able to reduce the gross non-performing financing ratio from 4.95% in June 2017 to 1.65%, resulting in a decline in the net NPF ratio from 3.74% to 0.88% (Gaddafi, 2019). The case above indicates that earnings management practices often result in fraudulent actions rather than genuine managerial efforts to manage profits (Yohana & Serly, 2020). In reality, earnings management practices do not occur in Islamic banking due to the inherent Sharia principles applied in this banking system (Suryanto, 2017). However, several studies have shown the existence of earnings management practices in Islamic banking, including those conducted by Illahi (2019), Rohmaniyah et al. (2018), Quttainah et al. (2013), Ugbede et al. (2013), and Zainuldin, Mohd Haniff, and Lui (2018). Their research found evidence of earnings management practices within Islamic banks. This indicates that managers in Islamic banking may have personal interests that lead them to engage in earnings management practices.

In substance, earnings management can be viewed from various perspectives. Many people believe it may be carried out as part of a planned action and represents one of the policies implemented by management for the benefit of the company. However, some consider earnings management a prohibited practice because it can harm users of the company's financial statements (Rice, 2016). Earnings management refers to practices used by company management to manipulate financial statements, making them appear better than the actual performance. These practices may include delaying the recognition of expenses, manipulating accounting estimates, or using accounting methods that produce more favorable financial reports (Handayani & Hebrew, 2020).

The impact of earnings management on a company can be complex, with both positive and negative effects depending on the perspective and time frame considered. Earnings management may create the perception that the company's financial performance is better, which can increase investor confidence and potentially enhance the company's value (Olatunji & Juwon, 2020). In the long term, successful earnings management practices may raise the company's stock price and create added value for shareholders. However, if such practices are revealed, they can damage investor trust and lead to a decline in the company's value.

Management profit occurs due to information asymmetry between management as agents and company owners as principals (Suryanto, 2014). Furthermore, earnings management has become a corporate culture practiced by companies worldwide. Many factors affect companies to engage in earnings management practices, with the disclosure of sustainability reporting being one significant factor. The disclosure of sustainability reporting has now become a trend and an obligation for companies, as it helps ensure business continuity (Trisnawati, 2016).

Sustainability reporting refers to the disclosure of an organization's economic, environmental, and social policies, impacts, and performance within the context of sustainable development. Companies that provide sustainability disclosures through sustainability reporting show their social awareness and commitment to environmental conservation to financial report users. Disclosing activities related to social responsibility has become a common practice among analysts, investors, and other interested stakeholders (Wulandari, 2016) .

A company's objective in disclosing social responsibility activities may not solely be a form of transparency to financial report users, as suggested by the "transparent financial reporting hypothesis." However, it may also serve as an opportunistic effort to attract analysts, investors, or other users, which aligns with the "opportunistic financial reporting hypothesis" (Kim et al., 2012). If a company's goal in expressing social responsibility aligns with the opportunistic financial reporting hypothesis, then the company will be more likely to engage in earnings management.

Research on the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and earnings management was first explored by Chih, Shen, and Kang (2008) and Prio, Surroca, and Tribo (2008). The study conducted by Prior et al. (2008) found a positive effect between earnings management practices and corporate social responsibility. Meanwhile, Chih et al. (2008) found a negative relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and earnings management when earnings management was measured using income smoothing. Furthermore, Astuti (2021) revealed that companies can enhance the disclosure of sustainability reports in terms of both quality and quantity, which in turn helps build greater trust among the public and stakeholders.

Companies that disclose sustainability reporting through annual reports or supplementary reports can overcome the limitations of traditional financial statements. Moreover, companies that engage in activities without providing adequate social responsibility are perceived as ethical entities that do not commit violations such as earnings manipulation or earnings management (Astuti, 2021). However, the many positive impacts of sustainability reporting are sometimes misused by companies to create a positive corporate image, aiming to conceal the opportunistic managerial behavior involved in earnings management. From the perspective of legitimacy theory, corporate disclosure is viewed as a means to gain legitimacy from society. Companies and society are bound by a social contract that aims to create alignment between the company's social values and the social norms of the community (Kepakisan & Budiasih, 2022) .

Corporate governance emerged as an effort to establish more transparent corporate management, enabling companies to enhance their performance by supervising or monitoring managerial actions and ensuring management accountability to stakeholders within a regulatory framework (Nasution & Setiawan, 2007). By implementing corporate governance (CG), the issue of misalignment of interests between principals and agents can be addressed through effective corporate management. Earnings management behavior carried out by management can be minimized by applying proper corporate governance practices (Agustia, 2013) .

Corporate governance from an Islamic perspective is referred to as Islamic Corporate Governance. Islamic Corporate Governance integrates all concepts and behaviors in sound and sustainable business governance, grounded in the values of *tawhid* (monotheism), which serve as the foundation for understanding corporate governance. One of the parties that holds an important and distinct role in implementing Good Corporate Governance within Islamic banking is the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS). The primary duty of the DPS is to provide advice and recommendations to the board of directors, as well as to supervise banking activities to ensure compliance with Sharia principles (Nurhayati et al., 2019).

The existence of the Sharia Supervisory Board and the agency conflicts that occur can be resolved through an effective supervisory function within good corporate governance. According to the study by Pramithasari & Yasa (2017), the Sharia Supervisory Board is considered one of the components of good corporate governance, serving as the supervisory function of Islamic institutions. The increasing number of Sharia Supervisory Boards in Islamic banking indicates a greater presence of supervisory functions, thereby allowing Islamic banking operations to be more effectively monitored (Rahayu Lestari et al., 2022).

This is also in line with agency theory and legitimacy theory. Agency theory explains that the presence of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) can reduce information asymmetry. Meanwhile, according to legitimacy theory, the existence of an active and interactive DPS also functions as an instrument that supports the company's legitimacy by demonstrating high transparency and accountability, thereby fostering long-term public and investor trust. Thus, within the framework of legitimacy theory, the DPS serves as a governance mechanism that strengthens integrity, sustainability disclosure, and minimizes earnings management practices.

This study analyzes earnings management practices occurring in Islamic banking. Several previous studies have shown different results, and research on earnings management in Islamic banking remains limited. Furthermore, earnings management itself has varying impacts depending on how companies utilize it. In Islamic banking, these institutions operate based on the principles of Islamic economics and conduct their activities in accordance with Sharia principles. However, many Islamic banks still engage in earnings management practices that harm investors, indicating that Islamic bank managers may have personal interests that lead to such earnings management behavior. Furthermore, Islamic banking shows that the Sharia principles governing its operations have not been fully implemented. This study also highlights the role of sustainability reporting in earnings management, as the objective disclosure of company activities alone is insufficient to meet social needs and provide corporate transparency for financial statement users. However, many companies use sustainability reporting to create a positive corporate image with the intention of concealing opportunistic managerial behavior related to earnings management (Kepakisan & Budiasih, 2022). In addition, the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic banking serves not only as a positive legal advisor but also as an advisor on Islamic law. The presence of the DPS reflects the extent to which Islamic banking operations comply with Sharia principles. Therefore, optimal supervision is necessary to produce financial reports that are genuine and free from manipulation (Ilyas, 2021)

This research aims to determine the extent of earnings management in Islamic banking, given that Islamic banks, as financial institutions operating under Sharia principles, should not engage in any form of manipulation in financial report disclosures. It also examines the role of sustainability reporting in addressing earnings management issues, strengthened by the presence of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic banking, which can help mitigate irregularities in the disclosure of company financial reports. Therefore, this study is titled “*The Role of the Sharia Supervisory Board in Moderating the Relationship Between Sustainability Reporting and Earnings Management in Islamic Banking.*”

Theoretical Framework

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory is an idea that explains how a social contract between a company and society is formed. According to this theory, in order to be accepted by society, a company must disclose how its social activities are carried out so that it can ensure the company's sustainability (Murni & Ayem, 2021). From the perspective of legitimacy theory, a company's disclosure is considered a means to obtain legitimacy from society. Companies and society have a bound relationship due to the existence of a social contract. This contract aims to create alignment between the company's social values and societal norms.

In this case, the sustainability reporting serves as a means for companies to obtain, maintain, or restore legitimacy in the eyes of the public and stakeholders. However, legitimacy theory also provides room for companies to strategically use sustainability reporting as a tool to conceal earnings management practices.

Theory of Agility

Agency theory explains the relationship between the principal and the agent. The party referred to as the company owner (principal) grants authority and delegates decision-making power to another party (agent), who is then responsible to the principal for the decisions and actions taken (Razak & Helmy, 2020). Agency theory describes the dynamics of the relationship between the principal (owner) and the agent (management), where differences in interests often lead to conflicts. Management generally has greater access to information than the principal, resulting in information asymmetry. This condition may encourage management to take opportunistic actions, such as engaging in earnings management practices to present financial performance that meets the expectations of shareholders and other interested stakeholders.

Earnings Management

Earnings management is an intentional intervention in the external financial reporting process with specific objectives to obtain personal benefits. It is generally aimed at personal interests, such as maximizing managerial welfare (Ramadhan & Firmansyah, 2022). Earnings management portrays financial statements as manipulated in terms of quality (Saragih, 2019). According to Ardekani et al. (2012), earnings management can

be defined through three conceptual frameworks. First, earnings management serves as an information flexibility tool in accounting, acting as a signal of the information completeness possessed by company managers for other shareholders. Second, earnings management serves as a tool in accounting, benefiting both opportunistic and optimistic individuals. Third, earnings management involves manipulating data to benefit managers.

Sustainability Reporting

The concept of sustainability reporting first emerged from the *Triple Bottom Line* framework proposed by John Elkington (1997), who argued that if a company wants to maintain its long-term sustainability, it must focus on the “3Ps”: pursuing **profit**, caring for and contributing to the welfare of **people**, and actively participating in protecting the **planet** (Puspita Sari & Cahyo Utomo, 2019).

Sharia Supervisory Board

Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 11/33/PBI/2009 concerning the implementation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) for Islamic commercial banks and Islamic business units stipulates that the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) is responsible for providing advice and recommendations to the board of directors, as well as supervising banking activities to ensure compliance with Sharia principles. However, according to the Decree of the National Sharia Council Number 3 of 2000, the DPS is part of a Sharia financial institution and is established with the approval of the National Sharia Council (Murdiansyah, 2021).

Research Model

Figure 1. Research Model

Hypotheses

The Effect of Sustainability Reporting on Earnings Management

This is based on legitimacy theory, which explains that companies continuously strive to ensure that their operations comply with legitimate and lawful social rules and norms (Kepakisan & Budiasih, 2022). In this context, sustainability reporting is highly important because it enables stakeholders, including the public, to understand all forms of corporate responsibility toward society and the surrounding environment. Sustainability reporting is one of the tools companies use to obtain, maintain, or restore legitimacy in the eyes of the public and stakeholders. By disclosing social, environmental, and corporate governance information, companies aim to show their commitment to social responsibility in line with societal expectations. However, legitimacy theory also provides room for companies to strategically use sustainability reporting as a tool to conceal earnings management practices. Research results by Astuti (2021) shows that through sustainability reporting, the better the quality and quantity of disclosures made by companies, the higher the level of trust gained from the public and stakeholders, thereby reducing the level of earnings management.

H₁: Sustainability Reporting has a negative effect on Earnings Management.

Moderation of the Sharia Supervisory Board on the Effect of Sustainability Reporting on Earnings Management

Islamic banking is a business entity that prioritizes trust; therefore, to enhance public confidence in Islamic banks, the implementation of good corporate governance principles is required. Similarly, in the disclosure of sustainability reporting, one aspect that can be affected by the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) is management policy. This aligns with both agency theory and legitimacy theory. Agency theory explains that the presence of the DPS can reduce information asymmetry, as the conflict of interest between the agent (manager) and the principal (stakeholder) gives rise to information asymmetry, which is a condition in which the agent possesses more actual company information than the principal, making it not effective for the principal to monitor the agent's actions (Puspita & Dwi, 2019). In Sharia-based companies, the existence of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) becomes an important factor that can moderate this relationship. The DPS plays a role in ensuring that corporate practices, including sustainability reporting, truly comply with Sharia principles and Islamic ethical values. An active and interactive DPS also functions as an instrument that supports corporate legitimacy by showing high levels of transparency and accountability, thereby building long-term public and investor trust. Thus, within the framework of legitimacy theory, the DPS serves as a governance mechanism that strengthens integrity, enhances sustainability disclosure, and minimizes harmful practices.

Thus, through the presence of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS), the disclosure of a company's sustainability reporting can be strengthened (Nurhikmah et al., 2018). When a company discloses good sustainability reporting, it cannot be separated from the role of the DPS, which functions as a supervisor in all activities carried out by Islamic banking.

This supervisory role helps reduce the occurrence of fraud or earnings management practices driven by personal interests.

The research conducted by Hastuti (2017) shows that corporate governance itself affects earnings management. Research by Andry (2018) states that implementing Good Corporate Governance (GCG) can prevent manipulative actions in various forms due to the presence of adequate control mechanisms. This is also consistent with the findings of (Kepakisan & Budiasih, 2022), which indicates that the quality of good corporate governance strengthens the negative effect of sustainability reporting disclosure on earnings management in financial and banking companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2016–2020. Meanwhile, research by Suryanto, (2017) shows that the size of the Sharia Supervisory Board does not reduce the level of earnings management in Islamic banks.

H₂: The Sharia Supervisory Board strengthens the negative effect of Sustainability Reporting on Earnings Management.

Research Methods

This study used a quantitative approach. As explained by Sugiyono (2016), the quantitative approach is also referred to as the traditional method because it has long been used in research and often serves as the basis for subsequent studies. This study aimed to examine the effect of sustainability reporting disclosure on earnings management, with the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) as a moderating variable and several control variables as model balancers.

The object of this research was Islamic banking companies registered with the Financial Services Authority (OJK). The study was conducted over a five-year period, from 2019 to 2023. The population in this study included all Islamic commercial banks registered with the OJK during the specified period. The sampling technique used was a non-probability method with a purposive approach, involving the selection of samples based on specific predetermined criteria. The criteria included the following items in Table 1.

Table 1. Predetermined criteria for sample

No	Criteria	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Total
1.	Islamic Commercial Banks registered with the Financial Services Authority (OJK) during 2019–2023	14	14	15	13	13	69
2.	Islamic Commercial Banks that did not publish a Sustainability Report during 2019–2023.	5	1	3	0	0	(9)
Total banks meeting the criteria							60
Observation years 2019-2023							5
Total final research samples							300

In this study, several variables were used. The independent variable is sustainability reporting, which was measured using the Sustainability Report Disclosure Index (SRDI) based on the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) guidelines.

The dependent variable is earnings management, which is proxied by Discretionary Loan Loss Provisions (DLLP). DLLP is obtained through three stages. First, the total Loan Loss Provision (LLP) is calculated using regression on the variables Current Non-Performing Financing (NPF), changes in NPF, and changes in total loans. Second, the Non-Discretionary LLP is calculated. Third, the DLLP value is obtained from the difference between the total LLP and the Non-Discretionary LLP. This measurement model refers to Kanagaretnam et al. (2004), Kwak et al. (2009), and Sandra (2018). The moderating variable in this study is the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS), which is measured based on the number of DPS members listed in each bank’s annual report. A larger number of DPS members is assumed to strengthen the effect of sustainability reporting on earnings management practices.

The data analysis technique used in this study was forecasting through panel data regression analysis with the assistance of EViews software. Panel data is a combination of time-series data and cross-sectional data. Since the number of samples may differ across years, an unstructured panel data technique was applied. The unstructured panel data analysis can be conducted using three methods. The regression equation is as follows:

$$EM_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(SE_{it}) + (DER_{it}) + (ROA_{it}) + (SIZE_{it}) + e_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$EM_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(SE_{it}) + \beta_2(DPS_{it}) + (DER_{it}) + (ROA_{it}) + (SIZE_{it}) + e_{it} \dots \dots (2)$$

$$EM_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(SE_{it}) + \beta_2(DPS_{it}) + \beta_1(SE_{it}) * DPS_1 + (DER_{it}) + (ROA_{it}) + (SIZE_{it}) + e_{it} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics describe the data of the research variables, including earnings management, sustainability reporting, leverage, profitability, and firm size, in Islamic banking institutions registered with the Financial Services Authority (OJK) during the 2019–2023 period. The table below presents the median, mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation values for each research variable.

Table 2. Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis Test

Statistics	EM	SRDI	DPS	DER	ROA	UK
Mean	28.71000	0.431833	0.800167	1.387333	1.059500	1.945333
Median	23.69500	0.400000	0.690000	1.215000	1.090000	1.840000
Maximum	96.19000	0.710000	1.390000	3.710000	3.690000	3.260000
Minimum	-17.78000	0.230000	0.690000	0.370000	0.000000	0.000000
Std Dev	20.57179	0.128769	0.209556	0.774944	0.833800	0.693978
Skewness	0.770329	0.168252	1.579914	1.390671	1.075222	-0.140331
Kurtosis	3.918142	1.970393	4.100745	4.936092	4.537042	3.791087

Statistics	EM	SRDI	DPS	DER	ROA	UK
Jarque-Bera	8.041534	2.933314	27.99037	28.71080	17.46727	1.761474
Probability	0.017939	0.230695	0.000001	0.000001	0.000161	0.414477
Sum	1722.600	25.91000	48.01000	83.24000	63.57000	116.7200
Sum Sq Dev	24968.71	0.978298	2.590898	35.43177	41.01808	28.41469
Observations	60	60	60	60	60	60

Based on Table 2, the results of the descriptive statistical analysis test can be explained as follows:

1. It is found that the earnings management (EM) variable has the lowest value of -17.78000 and the highest value of 96.19000. This shows that the EM values range between -17.78000 and 96.19000. The mean value of earnings management (EM) is less than 0, with a standard deviation of 20.57179. The mean value being greater than the standard deviation indicates that the data variation within the research sample is relatively small. The skewness value of 0.770329 indicates a right-skewed distribution, while the kurtosis value of 3.918142, which is higher than 3 (the normal value), suggests a slightly peaked or leptokurtic distribution. The Jarque-Bera test result of 8.041534 with a probability value of 0.017939 (< 0.05) indicates that the EM data are not normally distributed. The sum value of 1722.600 shows that when all EM values from the 60 observations are added together, the total is 1722.600. Meanwhile, the sum of squared deviations of 24968.71 means that the total squared deviation of EM from its mean value (28.71) is 24968.71.

2. It is found that the Sustainability Report Disclosure Index (SRDI) variable has the lowest value of 0.230000 and the highest value of 0.710000. This shows that the SRDI values range between 0.230000 and 0.710000. The mean value of the Sustainability Report Disclosure Index (SRDI) is 0.431833, with a standard deviation of 0.128769. The mean value being greater than the standard deviation indicates that the data variation within the research sample is relatively small. The skewness value of 0.168252 (close to 0) and the kurtosis value of 1.970393 (below 3) indicate a relatively normal distribution with a slightly flat peak (platykurtic). The Jarque-Bera test result of 2.933314 with a probability value of 0.230695 (> 0.05) shows that the SRDI data are normally distributed. The sum value of 25.91000 shows that when all SRDI values from the 60 observations are added together, the total is 25.91000. Meanwhile, the sum of squared deviations of 0.879298 means that the total squared deviation of SRDI from its mean value (0.431833) is 0.879298.

3. It is found that the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) variable has the lowest value of 0.690000 and the highest value of 1.390000. This indicates that the DPS values range between 0.690000 and 1.390000. The mean value of the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) is 0.800167, with a standard deviation of 0.209556. The mean value being greater than the standard deviation indicates that the data variation within the research sample is relatively small. The skewness value of 1.579914 shows a right-skewed distribution, while the kurtosis value of 4.100745 indicates a highly peaked (leptokurtic) distribution. The Jarque-Bera test result of 27.99037 with a probability value of 0.000001 (< 0.05) shows that the DPS data are not normally distributed. The sum value of 48.01000 shows that when all DPS values from the 60 observations are added together, the total is

48.01000. Meanwhile, the sum of squared deviations of 2.590898 means that the total squared deviation of DPS from its mean value (0.800167) is 2.590898.

4. It is found that the leverage (DER) variable has the lowest value of 0.370000 and the highest value of 3.710000. This indicates that the DER values range between 0.370000 and 3.710000. The mean value of leverage (DER) is 1.387333, with a standard deviation of 0.774944. The mean being smaller than the standard deviation shows that the data variation within the research sample is relatively large. The skewness value of 1.390671 indicates a right-skewed distribution, while the kurtosis value of 4.936092 suggests a leptokurtic distribution. The Jarque-Bera test result of 28.71080 with a probability value of 0.000001 (< 0.05) indicates that the leverage data are not normally distributed. The sum value of 83.24000 indicates that when all DER values from the 60 observations are combined, the total is 83.24000. Meanwhile, the sum of squared deviations of 35.43177 means that the total squared deviation of DER from its mean value (1.387333) is 35.43177.

5. It is found that the profitability (ROA) variable has the lowest value of 0.00000 and the highest value of 3.690000. This indicates that the ROA values range between 0.00000 and 3.690000. The mean value of profitability (ROA) is 1.059500, with a standard deviation of 0.833800. The mean being greater than the standard deviation indicates that the variation in the data within the research sample is relatively small. The skewness value of 1.075222 shows a right-skewed distribution, while the kurtosis value of 4.537042 (> 3) indicates a more peaked (leptokurtic) distribution. The Jarque-Bera test result of 17.46727 with a probability value of 0.000161 (< 0.05) indicates that the ROA data are not normally distributed. The sum value of 63.57000 shows that when all ROA values from the 60 observations are added together, the total is 63.57000. Meanwhile, the sum of squared deviations of 41.01808 means that the total squared deviation of ROA from its mean value (1.059500) is 41.01808.

6. It is found that the firm size (UK) variable has the lowest value of 0.00000 and the highest value of 3.260000. This indicates that the firm size values range between 0.00000 and 3.260000. The mean value of firm size (UK) is 1.945333, with a standard deviation of 0.693978. The mean being smaller than the standard deviation shows that the data variation within the research sample is relatively large. The skewness value of -0.140331 indicates that the distribution is nearly symmetrical, while the kurtosis value of 3.791087 shows a relatively peaked distribution. The Jarque-Bera test result of 1.761474 with a probability value of 0.414477 (> 0.05) indicates that the firm size (UK) data are normally distributed. The sum value of 116.7200 shows that when all UK values from the 60 observations are added together, the total is 116.7200. Meanwhile, the sum of squared deviations of 28.41469 means that the total squared deviation of firm size (UK) from its mean value (1.945333) is 28.41469.

Model Selection Test

In conducting panel data regression analysis, a model selection test was first performed to provide a clear overview of the stages of data processing. There are three available models, namely the Common Effect Model (CEM), the Fixed Effect Model (FEM), and

the Random Effect Model (REM). Among these three, the most appropriate model will be selected. The three stages of model selection are as follows:

Table 3. Model Selection Analysis

No	Equation	Chow Test	LM Test	Conclusion
1	$EM_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(SE_{it}) + (DER_{it}) + (ROA_{it}) + (SIZE_{it}) + e_{it}$	0.7042	0.2500	CEM
2	$EM_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(SE_{it}) + \beta_2(DPS_{it}) + (DER_{it}) + (ROA_{it}) + (SIZE_{it}) + e_{it}$	0.6113	0.2381	CEM
3	$EM_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(SE_{it}) + \beta_2(DPS_{it}) + \beta_1(SE_{it}) * DPS_1 + (DER_{it}) + (ROA_{it}) +$	0.6176	0.2304	CEM

Based on Table 3, the results of the Chow test conducted on equations 1, 2, and 3 show that the Chi-square probability values are greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that the selected model is the Common Effect Model (CEM). After determining that the chosen model is CEM, the next step is to perform the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test to determine whether the CEM model is more appropriate than the Random Effect Model (REM). The LM test results for regression models 1, 2, and 3 show probability values greater than 0.05, indicating that the most appropriate model to be used in this study is the Common Effect Model (CEM).

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

The normality test was conducted to determine whether the regression model in this study was normally distributed. To assess whether the model follows a normal distribution, the Jarque-Bera test was used. If the probability value is greater than 0.05, the regression model is considered to be normally distributed. Based on the results of the normality test, the regression equations 1, 2, and 3 are explained in Table 4.

Table 4. Normality Test Results

Regression Model	Probability	Description
Regression Model 1	0.512434	Normally Distributed
Regression Model 2	0.513180	Normally Distributed
Regression Model 3	0.521870	Normally Distributed

Based on the results of the normality test for regression models 1, 2, and 3, it is known that the probability values of all three models are greater than 0.05, indicating that the data are normally distributed.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to determine whether there is a variance inequality among observations in the regression model. If the probability value is > 0.05 , it means there is no heteroscedasticity problem, while if the probability value is < 0.05 , it indicates

the presence of heteroscedasticity. The results of the heteroscedasticity test are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Regression Model	Probability	Description
Regression Model 1	0.9136	No heteroscedasticity detected
Regression Model 2	0.9450	No heteroscedasticity detected
Regression Model 3	0.9225	No heteroscedasticity detected

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test for equations 1, 2, and 3, it is known that the probability values are > 0.05 . Therefore, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to examine whether the regression model shows any correlation among the independent variables. A good regression model should be free from multicollinearity. The multicollinearity test can be evaluated using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. If the VIF value is < 10 , it means there is no multicollinearity problem. The results of the multicollinearity test are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Multicollinearity Test Results

Regression Model	VIF	Description
Regression Model 1	< 10.00	No multicollinearity detected
Regression Model 2	< 10.00	No multicollinearity detected
Regression Model 3	< 10.00	No multicollinearity detected

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test for regression equations 1, 2, and 3, it is known that the VIF values for all research variables are < 10 . Therefore, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity.

Autocorrelation Test

The autocorrelation test was conducted to determine whether there is a correlation between the residual errors in the regression model at period t and the residual errors at the previous period ($t-1$). To assess whether the regression model in this study is free from autocorrelation, the Breusch-Godfrey Correlation Test was used. The decision criteria for the Breusch-Godfrey test are as follows: if the probability value is > 0.05 , the regression model does not experience autocorrelation; conversely, if the probability value is < 0.05 , autocorrelation is present.

Table 7. Autocorrelation Test

Regression Model	Probability	Description
Regression Model 1	0.3607	No autocorrelation detected
Regression Model 2	0.3589	No autocorrelation detected
Regression Model 3	0.3931	No autocorrelation detected

Based on the results of the autocorrelation test for regression equations 1, 2, and 3, the probability values of the regression models are > 0.05 . Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation problem in the models.

Model Fit Test

Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

The coefficient of determination was used to observe the percentage of the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. The higher the value of the coefficient of determination, the better the independent variables can explain the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination ranges between zero and one. If the coefficient of determination approaches 1, it indicates that the regression model has a strong effect on the dependent variable. Conversely, if it approaches 0, the independent variables have little effect on the dependent variable. The results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) test are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Results of the Determination Coefficient Test (R^2)

Regression Model	R-Squared	Adjusted R-Squared
Regression Model 1	0.6890	0.6664
Regression Model 2	0.6892	0.6603
Regression Model 3	0.6897	0.6545

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination test in regression model 1, the Adjusted R-squared value is 0.6890. This indicates that the variables of sustainability reporting and the control variables of leverage, profitability, and firm size can explain 68.90% of the effect on the earnings management variable, while other variables outside this study explain the remaining 31.10%.

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination test in regression model 2, the Adjusted R-squared value is 0.6892. This indicates that the variables of sustainability reporting, the Sharia Supervisory Board, and the control variables of leverage, profitability, and firm size can explain 68.92% of the earnings management variable, while other variables outside this study explain the remaining 31.08%.

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination test in regression model 3, the Adjusted R-squared value is 0.6897. This indicates that the variables of sustainability reporting, the Sharia Supervisory Board, and the control variables of leverage, profitability, and firm size can explain 68.97% of the earnings management variable, while other variables outside this study explain the remaining 31.03%.

F Test (Simultaneous Test)

The F test was conducted to determine the simultaneous effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The significance level used as the basis for decision-making was 5%. If the probability value of the F-statistic is < 0.05 , it means that the independent variables jointly have a significant effect on the dependent variable. The results of the F test are presented below:

Table 9. F Test Results

Regression Model	Prob.	Description
Regression Model 1	0.0000	Simultaneous Effect
Regression Model 2	0.0000	Simultaneous Effect
Regression Model 3	0.0000	Simultaneous Effect

Based on the results in Table 9, it is known that the probability value F is $0.0000 < 0.05$ in regression model 1, regression model 2, and regression model 3. This means that the independent variables together have a significant effect on earnings management, and this research model is accepted for testing using regression.

Hypothesis Test (t-Test)

The t-test is used to examine the partial effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. If the probability value is < 0.05 , it can be concluded that the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable, and vice versa. The results of the hypothesis test (t-test) are presented below:

Sustainability Reporting

The first hypothesis (H1) states that sustainability reporting has a negative effect on earnings management. Based on the results of the regression analysis, the probability value obtained is $0.0284 < 0.05$, with a regression coefficient of -29.5298 . This indicates that sustainability reporting has a negative and significant effect on earnings management; therefore, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is accepted.

Sustainability Reporting Moderated by the Sharia Supervisory Board

The second hypothesis (H2) states that the Sharia Supervisory Board strengthens the negative effect of sustainability reporting on earnings management. Based on the results of the regression analysis, the probability value obtained is $0.7486 > 0.05$, with a regression coefficient of 2.1864 . This indicates that the Sharia Supervisory Board does not moderate the negative effect of sustainability reporting on earnings management; therefore, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is rejected.

Leverage

Leverage has a regression coefficient value of 9.2294 with a probability value of $0.0008 < 0.05$, indicating that leverage has a positive and significant effect on earnings management.

Profitability

Profitability has a regression coefficient value of 18.4109 with a probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$, indicating that profitability has a positive and significant effect on earnings management.

Firm Size

Firm size has a regression coefficient value of 15.2047 with a probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$, indicating that firm size has a positive and significant effect on earnings management.

Results and Discussion

The Effect of Sustainability Reporting on Earnings Management

Based on the results of the regression analysis above, a significance value of $0.0284 < 0.05$ was obtained, with a regression coefficient of -29.5298. This means that sustainability reporting has a negative and significant effect on earnings management. The more extensive the sustainability reporting disclosed by the company, the lower the likelihood of earnings management practices. This occurs because the accountability and public oversight of companies that openly disclose their sustainability reporting increases, thereby reducing the possibility of earnings management practices.

Sustainability reporting serves as an essential tool to enhance corporate transparency and accountability. This report not only reflects the company's commitment to environmental and social sustainability but also shows the extent to which the company adheres to good corporate governance principles, thereby reducing earnings management practices. The information in the economic dimension of sustainability reporting can provide assurance of competitive capital strength and reduce risk for stakeholders. The study by Ernst and Young (2013) in Astuti (2021) stated that investors tend to prefer investing in organizations that are transparent regarding analytical accuracy and the information provided, as this reduces information asymmetry.

In legitimacy theory, it is assumed that companies continuously strive to ensure that their operations comply with legitimate rules, norms, and social responsibilities. Sustainability reporting is important for stakeholders, including the public, as it provides insight into all aspects of the company's response to society and the environment. Sustainability reporting is essential for progressive companies to communicate their economic, social, and environmental performance while considering the interests of their stakeholders. Consequently, with a higher level of sustainability reporting disclosure, earnings management practices will be lower.

The results of this study are consistent with stakeholder interest theory and agency theory, which state that the disclosure of non-financial information, such as sustainability reporting, can enhance external monitoring and management accountability, thereby reducing the incentives for earnings management. According to agency theory, there is a conflict of interest between managers and company owners. Managers have incentives to

manipulate financial statements to achieve certain targets, such as performance-based bonuses or maintaining investor confidence. However, with the increased disclosure of non-financial information through sustainability reporting, management tends to limit earnings management practices. Sustainability reporting enhances external monitoring by institutional investors, analysts, and the public, which encourages management to be more cautious in presenting financial information.

Agency theory explains that the conflict of interest between the agent and the principal causes information asymmetry, which becomes the reason for the occurrence of earnings management. This condition is considered risky for stakeholders in making relevant decisions, and ultimately, it may threaten the relationship between the agent and the principal. Therefore, to maintain the relationship between the two parties, earnings management practices must be minimized.

The results of this study align with research conducted by Kepakisan and Budiasih (2022), which showed that sustainability reporting negatively affects earnings management in financial and banking companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). Furthermore, the research by Sari and Utomo (2019) found that sustainability reporting negatively affects earnings management. Broader sustainability report disclosures made by companies are considered capable of reducing the occurrence of earnings management practices.

Moderation of the Sharia Supervisory Board on the Effect of Sustainability Reporting on Earnings Management

Based on the results of the regression analysis, the significance value was $0.7486 > 0.05$ with a regression coefficient of 2.1864. This means that the Sharia Supervisory Board does not moderate the effect of sustainability reporting on earnings management. This indicates that the Sharia Supervisory Board cannot strengthen or weaken the effect of sustainability reporting on earnings management. Companies with a Sharia Supervisory Board do not show significant differences in this relationship pattern compared to companies without one. This condition implies that the presence of the Sharia Supervisory Board has not yet functioned optimally as a monitoring mechanism for sustainability reporting.

Companies with a Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) do not show significant differences in their relationship patterns compared to those without one. This condition indicates that the presence of the DPS has not yet functioned optimally as a supervisory mechanism for sustainability reporting. The Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) has not been fully capable of reducing earnings management practices, particularly those related to sustainability reporting. The DPS tends to focus more on aspects of sharia compliance, such as the prohibition of riba (usury), gharar (uncertainty), and maysir (gambling), as well as ensuring the halal nature of business activities, rather than on the technical aspects of financial transparency and reporting. As a result, even though the company has disclosed sustainability reporting, the monitoring of accounting manipulation practices such as earnings management has not become the main focus of the DPS (Antoni et al., 2023).

Implications of Research Results

The sustainability reporting variable in banking companies registered with the Financial Services Authority (OJK) during the 2019–2023 period has a negative and significant effect on earnings management. Companies can enhance the quality and consistency of their sustainability reporting as a form of public accountability. Good sustainability reporting not only improves the company's public image but also strengthens the integrity of financial statements by reducing the tendency of management to manipulate earnings.

The Sharia Supervisory Board (SSB) variable does not moderate the relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings management. This indicates that the existence of the SSB has not yet been fully effective in carrying out its supervisory function over ethical financial practices. This finding implies the need to enhance the quality and capacity of the SSB by providing relevant training in accounting and sustainability reporting, as well as by strengthening its independence and involvement in corporate governance processes.

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